

Sachchar Report: Necessity and Implication

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Abstract

Do the Muslims of India bear responsibility for their present condition? Has it come about because they have gone wrong somewhere, somehow? Can it be attributed solely or even principally to the Muslim inability or incapacity to prevent partition and an unwillingness to cope with all the physical and psychological consequences emanating from it? Six decades after independence, the identity of the Indian Muslim has been defined, and defined successfully, in national and territorial terms. A younger generation of Muslims, confident and assertive, seeks its right to equality and wants it to be implemented in specific terms. It is also conscious of the lost time and opportunities. This sentiment was expressed by Rafiq Zakaria in his Hakeem Abdul Hameed Memorial Lectural in 2002, "others have travelled beyond the moon and the sun; we are still tangled in the first ray of the rising sun." This realization is to be welcomed.

Keywords Sachar Report, Necessity, Implication.

Introduction

The Muslims of India should proclaim, as Maulana Azad did in October, 1947, " Any fundamental decision about the density of India will remain incomplete without the consent of Muslims."

This realization is not at all baseless. The bulk of India Muslims suffer grave deprivation in social opportunity, because of lack of access to education, health care and other public services, and to employment. Forty- three percent of Muslims live below the official poverty line. Muslim Men's work participation rate is 48 percent and for Muslim women, it is just 9.6 percent. The literacy rate among Muslims is 59 percent below the national average of 65 percent. A half of rural Muslim children are illiterate, as are a third of urban children. Thus, it can be said that India has betrayed the solemn pledge it made sixty two years ago to build an inclusive, plural and secular society which would equitably integrate its religious minorities while respecting their distinct identities and honouring differences. This is particularly true to our largest minority community, Muslims, who constitute 13.4 percent of the population.

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to discuss about the necessity and implication of Sachar report.

Review of Literature

The data compiled by the sachar committee from 12 state show that Muslims hold a tiny 5.7 percent of Government Jobs. In states with a high Muslim Population (UP, Bihar and West Bengal) this ratio is less than a third of their population share. In Maharashtra, it is less than one- fifth. In West Bengal Muslim's share in state employment is 4.2 percent, whereas their population share is 25.2 percent. This figure shows how deep the systemic exclusion of Muslims is. In the elite cadre services such as the IAS, IPS and the IPS, Muslim representation is respectively 2.2 percent, 1.6 percent and 3 percent. In the armed forces, Muslim representation is around 2 percent.

The number of Muslim Lok Shaba MPs have varied between 21 and 49 or between just 4.3 and 6.6 of the strength of the House-Less than one- half the Muslims' population share.

Main Text

The present unacceptable situation cries for rectification through concrete action plan for the upliftment of Muslims in India. It should be remembered that sachar committee report is the first systematic study of the Muslim community in Independent India. Rajinder sachar committee was constituted by the Manmohan Singh Government and it submitted its report in November 2005. The following are the Main highlights of the sachar report

1. Set up equal opportunity commission to address concerns of deprived minority groups.
2. Create a National data bank on various socio-religious categories.
3. Designate a section of Muslims as SCs or Most backward castes and evolve affirmative action measures.
4. Institute a nomination procedure for participation of minorities in public bodies.
5. Initiate steps to increase the employment share of Muslims.
6. Provide legal Mechanisms to address complaints of discrimination.
7. Establish a delimitation procedure that rules out reserving constituencies with high minority population for S.Cs
8. Promote religious tolerance by initiating a process to evaluate textbooks for appropriate social values.
9. Evaluate the extent of development benefits for different socio-religious categories.
10. Evolve a university Grants Commission and link financial allocation to diversity in student population.
11. Evolve criteria to facilitate admissions to the most backward socio-religious categories in universities.
12. Provide financial and other support to initiatives built around occupations where Muslims are concentrated and the have growth potential.
13. Work out mechanism to link madrassas to higher secondary Schools and recognize madrassa degrees for eligibility in defence, civil and banking examinations.
14. Devise teacher-training components that highlight diversity and sensitise teachers to the aspirations of Muslims.
15. Set up a national wakf Development corporation with a revolving corpus fund of Rs. 500 Crores.

On the strength of its comprehensive research and analysis the report also highlights the fact that some sections of Muslim society are more unequal than others. It draws attention to the presence of descent based social stratification on the lines of the Hindu caste system among Indian Muslims and identified three social segments-Ashrafs, Ajlafas and Arzals. The traditional occupation of Arzals is similar to that of SC's. Most of them work as butchers, washer men, barber and scavengers.

Ajlafas are engaged in occupations similar to that of the Hindu. OBCs and a sizable section of them are also landowners, Ashrafs have suffered no social deprivation as they are converts from the Hindu upper castes. Arzals are essentially converts from untouchable Hindu communities and that the change in religion did not bring about any change in their social or economic status. A crucial recommendation of the sachar committee is the constitution of an equal opportunity commission to look into the grievances of deprived groups. The report also says that an example of such a policy tool is the British Race Relations Act.

No doubt, the recommendations of the sachar committee are aimed at a - very right direction. But it has to be seen what fate awaits the comprehensive report and recommendations of the sachar committee. Are the political parties of India really serious about implementing it?

The answer lies with our political class, especially those who commissioned the Sechar panel- Prime Minister Manmohan Singh and his untitled progressive Alliance government.

The initial reaction of Indian political parties to the report was on predictable lines. All parties barring the BJP and the Shiv Sena had welcomed it as a step in the right

direction. But in fact none of the political party is serious about implementing it. In the past also the report of Dr. Gopal Singh Committee was buried alive. This opinion is cemented by the fact the Sachar submitted its report in November 2005 and since then no concrete step has been taken for implementing it. Important point is that since November, 2005. Manmohan Singh led Congress government has been in power. Is more than 4 years not enough for arriving at a decision? The fact is that since independence, for most of the time, congress party has been in power. It is because of the programmes and policies of the congress party that Muslims are still socially and economically backward. India has progressed under the guidance of congress party but the fruits of progress did not reach to the Muslim community. Congress party is still following its old policy of attracting Muslim votes by making "false promises". Hence in near future the implementation of Sachar committee report will remain an illusion.

The initial reaction of BJP to this report was very reactionary. The BJP asserted that there commendations would not improve the lot of Muslims as they reflected a pseudo-vision, full of biases and prejudices. The BJP always accuses congress party of promoting a policy of Muslim appeasement. The Sachar committee rightly points out that Muslims in India carry a double burden of being labeled anti-national and as being appeased at the same time. In fact, the very formation of the sachar committee in March, 2005, was characterized by BJP as yet another act of Muslim appeasement.

Another dimension of this discussion is that if the government decides to implement the sachar report, the BJP and other Hindutva forces like VHP, RSS and Bajrang Dal will mount a shrill campaign, which may strengthen the chauvinist currents in politics. Indian history is full of such examples when the Britishers gave certain concessions to Muslims in the early part of the 20th century; it resulted in the rise of Hindu Mahasabha.

So far the implementation of the report is concerned, even within the ruling congress party, important leaders have different opinions. For example - former Minister Arjun Singh says that without amending the constitution Sachar report cannot be implemented. It is true that India is a secular country.

The constitution of our country does not permit any concession on the name of religion. But it can be said that we have already amended our constitution for more than 100 times. What is wrong if we amend it once again for implementing the sachar report? It should be remembered that the constitution of India gave reservation to SCs and STs only for first ten years after adoption of the constitution. Since then we have been amending our constitution to ensure that reservation to SCs and STs should continue because they still need it. It should also be noted that the implementation of Mandal commission Report also involved amendment of the constitution. If the Mandal commission report can be implemented, why we can't implement the sachar report for the betterment of needing Indians.

In the Indian context, where quotas are viewed as a means of empowerment, the sachar report must be implemented at the earliest. All political parties of India as well as the Indian civil society should realize that an overwhelming majority of Muslims are socially and economically backward.

Conclusion

No artificial hurdle should be created a fresh to prevent its implementation. If India has to progress, every section of society will have to progress. It must be remembered that if we fail to bring Muslims into the mainstream of social, political and economic life, we will fail in our quest to become the world leader. Former Prime Minister Manmohan Singh often talked about inclusive growth. He should remember that Muslims also come in the purview of inclusive growth.

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